

Otomys auratus
South East African Vlei Rat

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Group: Mammal

Size: Head-body 133-202 mm, tail 58-120 mm, ear 17-5-26 mm, hindfoot 21-38 mm; weight 63-211 g

Distribution:

Widely distributed within grasslands in the north-eastern parts of South Africa, Lesotho and Eswatini, into the Eastern Highlands of Zimbabwe.

Importance:

The South East African Vlei Rat is a vital component of South African biodiversity, contributing to ecosystem health through seed dispersal, soil aeration, and serving as prey for predators. Genomic data will inform conservation strategies, ensuring the species' survival and ecosystem stability maintenance.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 91.99 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 5.48 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 1.22 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 98.8% [Single: 98.0%, Duplicated: 0.8%]
Assembly N50: 2 781.9 kilobases
Contig number: 3 740

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